

A Comparative Study of Audit Software with Specific References to Forensic Audit and Statutory Audit

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Introduction to Audit

Finance is defined as the management of money and includes activities like investing, borrowing, saving and forecasting.

Audit software transparency provides information policy management security with vision of transparency in audit to secure access to business information and data resources.

Audit software programs designed to assist in examining and testing client accounting records.

Audit software is divided into 14 types they are external audit, internal audit, forensic audit, statutory audit, financial audit, tax audit, information technology audit, compliance audit, value for money audit, review financial statement, agreed upon procedures, integrated audit, special audit and operational audit.

In that two are important that is statutory audit and Forensic audit

Meaning of Statutory Audit

Statutory audit refers to the audit of an organization performed under a statute. For certain business organization or institutions, audits are mandatory, such organizations come under this category. In this type of audit, the rights, powers, duties and responsibilities of auditors are laid down by the statute which cannot be altered or curtailed by the client or auditor himself.

Statutory audit is reporting data in a structured enterprise resource planning in (ERP) system, and unstructured data is defined as information that either does not have a predefined manner. This may contain dates, number and facts that reside outside ERP system.

Meaning of Forensic Audit

A forensic audit is an examination and evaluation of a firm’s or individual’s financial records to derive evidence that can be used in a court of law or legal proceeding. Forensic auditing is a specialization within the field of accounting, and most large accounting firms have a forensic auditing department. Forensic audits require the expertise of accounting and auditing procedures as well as expert knowledge about the legal framework of such an audit.

A forensic audit has emerged as a new discipline, current practices have been changed in electronic business environment and rapid increase in fraudulent activities, despite taking many forms, the fraud is usually theft of funds and information or misuse of someone’s information about the assets which has been financial frauds prevailing in digital audit.

Statement of the Problem

Research was scarce in the field of audit transparency in connection with audit software, covering under the board umbrella of audit software from review of literature cited and hence it is evident that no solid research has taken place in above mentioned topic and that has paved the path to undertake this particular research with reference to audit software.

Research Gap

The above statement of the problem has given scope to take up research in the above mentioned research area.

Research Design

1. Category of Data: Secondary data.
2. Type Of research: Conceptual
3. Tools used in Analysis: Analog

Objectives of the Study

1. To study features of prominent audit soft wares.
2. To understand how the audit software works.
3. To study how transparency can be achieved through the audit software.

Limitation of the Study

1. Time constraint.
2. Place constraint.
3. Research is confined only to two types of audit soft wares.

Data Analysis and Interpretation in Terms its Features

1. Objectives

Statutory audit: To express opinion as to true and fair presentation

Forensic audit: To determine correctness of the accounts or whether any fraud has actually taken place

Interpretation: Forensic audit provide all the detailed information to auditor, about accounts and it examines all the books of accounts whether the fraud has taken place .but the statutory audit doesn’t fulfill this.

2. Techniques

Statutory audit: Substantive and compliance procedures

Forensic audit: Analysis of past trend and substantive or in-depth checking of selected transaction are done

Interpretation: forensic audit collects all information from past and gives in-depth information about accounts. Mainly to avoid frauds and statutory audit fails in this area.

3. Period

Statutory audit: Normally all transaction for the the particular accounting period are considered

Forensic audit: There is no such limitation while conducting forensic audit and accounts will be examined in detail from the beginning.

Interpretation: while conducting forensic audit there is no limitation to verify book of accounts. so that auditor has no limitation for examination of accounts. But we don't find this feature in statutory audit.

4. Management Presentation

Statutory audit: Auditor relies on the management certificate/ representation of management

Forensic audit: Independent verification of suspected/selected items carried out

Interpretation: For forensic audit independent verification are done there will be no involvement of any 3rd party. Whereas statutory audit fails in this.

5. Off Balance Sheet Items

Statutory audit: off balance sheet item are used to vouch the arithmetic accuracy and compliance with procedure.

Forensic audit: Regularity and propriety of these transaction /contract are examined.

Interpretation: In forensic audit, it is conducted with concerned auditor and contract are examined to avoid frauds. But in statutory audit we don't find this feature.

6. Adverse Finding

Statutory audit: If there are any adverse finding negative opinion or qualified opinion is expressed with/ without quantification.

Forensic audit: The auditor aims at legal determinations of fraud and also naming person behind such frauds.

Interpretation: In forensic audit the auditor mainly aims at legal way for auditing if any frauds.

If fraud is done it can be easily found out. But the same activity can't be performed in statutory audit.

Findings and Conclusion

Findings

1. It was found that the features of all the audit software are up to mark and in that the features of forensic audit stands extraordinary.
2. Audit software works on the basis of digitalization (computerization) and out of the audit software taken for research. Forensic audit works very well within the framework of the companies and it is a best as compare to statutory audit.
3. Transparency can be best achieve through the audit software which can be drastically bring down the fraudulent activities and in that forensic audit stands extraordinary.

Conclusion

Forensic audit has emerged as a new discipline, current practices have been changed in electronic business environment, mainly to avoid frauds. This new digitalized audit has changed the way of auditing.

Both forensic and statutory audit perspectives is to get true and fair presentation of financial statement.

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